
53. The scientific case for Gaia in 2000

AT THE START of another year, and now 22 years since Gaia was accepted by the advisory committees of the European Space Agency in 2000, and with a steady flow of scientific results now coming from the mission, I thought it could be of interest to look back at the scientific case that was prepared at that time, and which was included along with the early technical assessment, together used as the basis for the advisory structure's consideration of the mission, and its eventual selection.

WHEN A ROUND of competitive mission selection is announced by ESA, a considerable effort – generally spanning several years – will already have been devoted to preparing an overall mission concept (describing what the satellite and payload will look like in overall terms), a preliminary but authoritative technical assessment, and an outline of the overall mission organisation and management.

The formal Gaia ‘Concept and Technology Study’ ran between 1997–2000. What was at stake was its candidacy for the next cornerstone mission of the ESA science programme, part of ESA’s long-term scientific programme arising from the recommendations of the Horizon 2000+ Survey Committee in 1994.

The resulting report, ESA–SCI(2000)4, extended to almost 400 pages. It synthesised the preparatory activities of the ESA Study Scientist (Michael Perryman), the ESA Study Manager (Oscar Pace), the scientists throughout Europe and beyond already supporting the mission’s objectives, the various industrial contractors involved in preparatory technology activities, engineers in ESA’s technical support directorate, and representatives of ESA’s Spacecraft Operations Centre (ESOC).

AT THIS STAGE, throughout 1997–2000, I had set up the following advisory structure. I chaired the top-level Science Advisory Group (SAG), comprising just eight external scientists, together intended to cover those whose primary interest was in the overall scientific goals, those with an appropriate technical background, and at the same time covering some overall European geographical (and therefore also political) representation.

Guiding the mission through to selection in 2000, these members were K.S. de Boer (Bonn), G. Gilmore (Cambridge), E. Høg (Copenhagen), M.G. Lattanzi (Torino), L. Lindgren (Lund), X. Luri (Barcelona), F. Mignard (Grasse), and P.T. de Zeeuw (Leiden).

Within ESA, four other staff regularly supported the top-level SAG activities (Oscar Pace, Martin Hechler, Sergio Volonte, and Fabio Favata), with a further four from ESA’s Space Science Department providing additional inputs. From ESA’s technical directorate, 11 engineers provided specific support in the various areas of instrument design, manufacture and testing. Their expertise covered on-board data processing, radiation, thermal control, structure, antenna, communications, attitude and orbit control, CCDs, and basic angle monitoring.

Reporting to the Science Advisory Group were three ‘working groups’. The Science Working Group, jointly chaired by Tim de Zeeuw and Gerry Gilmore, comprised 18 scientists. The Instrument Working Group, chaired by Lennart Lindgren, comprised 16 people; and the Photometry Working Group, chaired by Fabio Favata, comprised 18 people. A further 50 European scientists supported these various activities as ‘Members at Large’.

The preparatory technical studies were undertaken through two principle study contracts issued by ESA, and again coordinated by the ESA Study Scientist and ESA Study Manager.

One of these industrial teams, Matra Marconi Space (Toulouse; now Airbus), led by Pierre Mérat and comprising around 15 engineers, focused their efforts on primary mirrors of a monolithic design. The other, Alenia (Torino), led by Stefano Cesare and comprising a similar number of support staff, focused on a (small-baseline) interferometric system.

ALREADY WITH AN OUTLINE instrument concept on the drawing board, and with a fairly comprehensive assessment of the astrometric and photometric accuracies that Gaia should achieve, we knew that the scientific breadth and reach of Gaia would be enormous, and a corresponding effort was invested in preparing and presenting the scientific case.

Within the 400-page Concept and Technology Study Report, the scientific case for Gaia ran to 100 pages. More than 60 (mainly ESA member-state) scientists contributed to the various sections, with the overall science case coordinated, and the report synthesised, by Tim de Zeeuw, Gerry Gilmore, and Michael Perryman.

THE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY presented the summary scientific case as follows, given here verbatim (while pointing out that the referenced mission accuracies targeted at the time, 10 microarcsec at 15 mag, were later descoped to around 25 microarcsec).

'Gaia will rely on the proven principles of ESA's Hipparcos mission to solve one of the most difficult yet deeply fundamental challenges in modern astronomy: to create an extraordinarily precise three-dimensional map of about one billion stars throughout our Galaxy and beyond. In the process, it will map their motions, which encode the origin and subsequent evolution of the Galaxy. Through comprehensive photometric classification, it will provide the detailed physical properties of each star observed: characterising their luminosity, temperature, gravity, and elemental composition. This massive stellar census will provide the basic observational data to tackle an enormous range of important problems related to the origin, structure, and evolutionary history of our Galaxy.

'Gaia will achieve this by repeatedly measuring the positions of all objects down to $V = 20$ mag. On-board object detection will ensure that variable stars, supernovae, burst sources, micro-lensed events, and minor planets will all be detected and catalogued to this faint limit. Final accuracies of 10 microarcsec at 15 mag, comparable to the diameter of a human hair at a distance of 1000 km, will provide distances accurate to 10 per cent as far as the Galactic Centre, 30 000 light years away. Stellar motions will be measured even in the Andromeda galaxy.

'Gaia's expected scientific harvest is of almost inconceivable extent and implication. Its main goal is to clarify the origin and history of our Galaxy, by providing tests of the various formation theories, and of star formation and evolution. This is possible since low mass stars live for much longer than the present age of the Universe, and therefore retain in their atmospheres a fossil record of their detailed origin. The Gaia results will precisely identify relics of tidally-disrupted accretion debris, probe the distribution of dark matter, establish the luminosity function for pre-main sequence stars, detect and categorise rapid evolutionary stellar phases, place unprecedented constraints on the age, internal structure and evolution of all stellar types, establish a rigorous distance scale framework throughout the Galaxy and beyond, and classify star formation and kinematical and dynamical behaviour within the Local Group of galaxies.

'Gaia will pinpoint exotic objects in colossal and almost unimaginable numbers: thousands of exoplanets will be discovered, and their orbits and masses determined; tens of thousands of brown dwarfs and white dwarfs will be identified; some 100 000 extragalactic supernovae will be discovered and details passed to ground-based observers for follow-up observations; solar system studies will receive a massive impetus through the detection of tens of thousands of new minor planets; inner Trojans and even new trans-Neptunian objects, including Plutinos, may also be discovered.

'Gaia will follow the bending of star light by the Sun and major planets, over the entire celestial sphere, and therefore directly observe the structure of space-time—the accuracy of its measurement of General Relativistic light bending may reveal the long-sought scalar correction to its tensor form. The PPN parameters γ and β , and the solar quadrupole moment J_2 , will be determined with unprecedented precision. New constraints on the rate of change of the gravitational constant, \dot{G} , and on gravitational wave energy over a certain frequency range, will be obtained.'

Elsewhere, in the overview of Gaia's scientific goals, we also underlined that... *Gaia is timely as it builds on recent intellectual and technological breakthroughs. Current understanding and exploration of the early Universe, through microwave background studies (e.g., Planck) and direct observations of high-redshift galaxies (HST, NGST, VLT) have been complemented by theoretical advances in understanding the growth of structure from the early Universe up to galaxy formation. Serious further advances require a detailed understanding of a 'typical' galaxy, to test the physics and assumptions in the models. The Milky Way and the nearest Local Group galaxies uniquely provide such a template.*

IT IS INDEED SATISFYING to see these far-reaching predictions being achieved within just two decades.

In another essay here, Galactic Tracers by Design, I go more into how Gaia targeted very specific measurement goals, formulated in terms of limiting magnitude and astrometric accuracy. Gaia's limiting magnitude of around 20–21 mag, for example, was a requirement resulting from an examination of what types of stars, in different regions of our Galaxy, should be measured.

THE STUDY REPORT also included a section on specific questions that could be tackled by high-accuracy astrometry, but which remain largely inaccessible even to Gaia: rich grounds for future space missions. This included the cores of globular clusters, the Galactic centre, inhomogeneities of the Galactic gravitational potential, and geometric cosmology, viz. studying the transverse motions of distant galaxies and quasars, independently of a dynamical model of the Universe.